

Agent_Caf: A tool to support financial-decision making for smallholder coffee producers

Technical documentation

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1. Introduction

Agent_Caf is a scenario-based finance and carbon-accounting tool for smallholder farmers growing coffee (Café Arabica) in agroforestry systems, which re-implements in R the logic of the original model “Modelo agroforestal de café Arábica” (Simonit et al, 2020) and adds new features to it. Agent_Caf reads in a technical parameter sheet (.csv) describing initial management, cost and income parameters for a representative farm and calculates annual cashflows for a time horizon set to 20 years, along with key financial indicators (e.g., transition costs, net present value and internal rate of return). It also quantifies climate-relevant ecosystem services of agroforestry via a farm-level carbon balance account (CO₂ absorption – emissions from fertilization).

In the current version 1.0, Agent_Caf focuses on Café Arábica production in agroforestry, and unlike the original Excel-based model (Simonit et al, 2020), provides an extensible modular structure. The model is designed so users can flexibly add MILPA production (maiz, beans, pumpkin), apiculture for honey production or mix in cash-crops (banana, cacao, cardamom) to the basic coffee agroforestry farm model. When users choose these add-ons, the cash flow, carbon balance, and financial parameters of the farm system are re-calculated and updated. The tool also provides the option to sell carbon credits as an additional income source for farmers to a (hypothetical) carbon market. It further allows to investigate the economic impact of a number of coffee yield reduction scenarios under varying environmental and climatic conditions.

Agent_Caf has an in-built scenario explorer for loan repayment schemes with an adjustable interest rate for financing costs. It thereby aims to inform financial institutions (banks) and smallholder farmers alike on the financial implications and feasibility of sustainable farm management decisions.

Agent_Caf is developed as part of the SAbERES project. SAbERES promotes adaptation to climate change among small-scale Mexican rural producers across ten key Mexican states by combining financial tools, Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) strategies, and technical support. Future versions of the tool aim to extend the same framework to additional EbA practice options (e.g., milpa with agroforestry, cattle herds within silvopasture). Further, it is planned to adapt and test the tool to other regions of coffee production within Mexico (and beyond) by adjusting the yield scenarios to location-specific environmental-climatic conditions and introducing regional parameterization for labour and other relevant input costs.

2. Overview

2.1 Purpose and outputs

Agent_Caf runs in R and produces the following core outputs for a chosen scenario:

- Annual total cashflow and optionally added systems (MILPA, cashcrops, apiculture). It calculates investment costs, variable costs, fixed costs, income, financing, and net cashflow for the farm and each system.
- Net Present Value (NPV) and additional finance indicators (e.g., transition costs, updated total cost, updated total benefits, and IRR).
- Direct and indirect emissions time series from organic fertilizer (including harvest residues) and synthetic fertilizer application on the field (kg CO₂e/ha).
- Tree biomass, carbon stock, CO₂ absorption (tCO₂/ha), and (optionally) carbon revenue from incremental sequestration at a given CO₂ price.
- A carbon-balance time series combining emissions and absorption (tCO₂/ha).

2.2 Time horizon and units

The model runs on an annual time step for years $t = 0, 1, \dots, 20$. Monetary values are in MXN per hectare (MXN/ha) unless stated otherwise. Emissions are computed in kg CO₂e/ha and converted to tCO₂e/ha when presented in the carbon balance. CO₂ absorption is in tCO₂/ha.

3. Data inputs and preprocessing

3.1 Input workbook and parameter sheets

Agent_Caf 1.0 uses at the moment a set of real technical, cost and income parameters that have been produced as part of the project: *“Investment Plan for Low Emission Rural Development in the State of Oaxaca”* by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in collaboration with the Government of the State of Oaxaca in the framework of the initiatives promoted by the Governors' Climate and Forests Task Force (GCF Task Force) (Simonit et al. 2020). Agent_Caf adds new scenarios to the baseline technical data to explore different yields, carbon revenue, and loan repayment schemes.

The tool reads a csv file containing parameters for multiple systems. In version 1.0 the following sheets are used:

- Farm: global parameters (discount_rate, interest_rate, carbon price).
- Farm_parameter, MILPA_parameter, Cafe_parameter, Apiculture_parameter: annual quantities (year 0 through 20) and unit values.
- emission_parameter: emissions factors and activity data used to compute GHG emissions by emission source.
- biomass_parameter: tree growth trajectories (diameter, height) and species identifier used in the biomass/absorption module.

3.2 Long-format economic table

Each system sheet is converted in R into a unified long-format table `econ_long` with columns:

- `system`, `type` (`econ_type`), `product`, `production_cycle`, `activity`, `input`, `description`, `unit`, `unit_value`, `year`, `quantity`, `total_mxn`.
- `total_mxn` is computed as `quantity × unit_value` for each row and year.

$$total_mxn_{i,t} = q_{i,t} \times u_i$$

4. Scenario framework

4.1 Scenario object

A scenario is a structured list created by `saberes_scenario()`. It captures model scope (full vs café-only), system toggles (MILPA, cash-crops, Apiculture), financing settings, carbon-credit settings, and coffee yield settings. The scenario is stored inside the output list for traceability.

4.2 System tagging and scoping

Rows in `econ_long` are tagged with an `system_tag` to enable scope selection without rewriting downstream finance code. For example, café income rows are tagged as `coffee_crop`, tree planting rows as `tree_component`, and certain product-NA rows as `coffee_overhead`.

In the café-only scope, the model keeps: (i) baseline Farm investment and fixed costs, (ii) `coffee_crop`, `tree_component`, `coffee_overhead`, and optional add-ons such as cover crops, milpa, apiculture, cash crops, and meliferous species according to the scenario toggles.

4.3 Coffee yield scenarios

Coffee yield is represented through the `Café_parameter` income rows for `product = cafe_arabica` (`yield*price`). The Oaxaca farm data sheet provides a yield trajectory for “optimal productive potential” considering rainfall, months with wet soil, temperatures and slopes (see table 1). `Agent_Caf` then allows the user to explore scenario-driven yield reductions by multiplying coffee yields with a year-specific multiplier m_t . The multiplier is built on data reported for producing coffee in less optimal environmental and climate conditions in Oaxaca, resulting in lower productive potential and thus lower yields (Simonit et al., 2020). `Agent_Caf` accounts for yield reduction impacts on labour cost changes in the harvest and post-harvesting phase. We assume that daily labour input for the activity “harvesting” and “bean selection” is proportional to yields, resulting in lower variable costs in low yield scenarios.

Table 1: Environmental and Climatic conditions for coffee yields:

yield (t/ha/yr)	Optimal(2.0 -2.6)	moderate (1.9 -1.5)	low (1.4 -1.0)	Unit
rainfall	1500 - 2000	2000-2500/1300-1500	<1300	mm
wet soil	9 to 10	8 and 10	7 and 12	months
temperature	19 -22	22-24 and 18-19	24-25 and 17 -18	°C
slope	<30	30 -35	35 -45	
altitude	1200 -1700	1700 -2000	2000-2500 /600 -900	meters above sea level
soils	Chernozem, Kastanozem, Luvisol medium/fine texture	Cambisol Lixisol Umbrisol medium/fine texture	Cambisol Chemozem Kastanisem coarse texture	

(adapted from Simonit et al., 2020)

Yield target levels (t/ha of coffee cherries) supported in v1.0 that users can freely choose:

- optimum: 2.6 t/ha
- moderate: 2.0 t/ha
- moderate_low: 1.5 t/ha
- low: 1.0 t/ha

These targets then result in adjusted yields:

$$y_{t,adj}^{coffee} = m_t y_t^{coffee}$$

In addition, users can choose two yield path scenarios allowing them to freely investigate economic and financial impacts depending on when during the specified time horizon yield reduction may occur and at what magnitude:

- **Scenario 1** (step): yield drops to the target level from a specified year onward:

$$m_t = 1 \text{ for } t < t_o; m_t = f \text{ for } t \geq t_o$$

- **Scenario 2** (ramp_18_20): yield declines linearly from the optimum level between years and then stays at the target level for the remaining years.

Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$m_t = 1 \text{ if } t < t_s;$$

$$m_t = 1 + \frac{t - t_s}{t_e - t_s} (f - 1) \text{ if } t_s \leq t < t_e;$$

$$m_t = f \text{ if } t \geq t_e$$

For transparency, the model stores a per-year coffee yield time series (in t/ha) alongside multipliers in the output object (see Section 10).

5. Cashflow accounting

5.1 Income and cost aggregation

For each system s and year t , the model aggregates monetary flows from `econ_long` by “economic type”: investment, variable costs, fixed costs and income:

$$I_{s,t} = \sum_{i \in s, \text{type}=\text{investment}} \text{total_mxn}_{i,t}$$

$$V_{s,t} = \sum_{i \in s, \text{type}=\text{variable}} \text{total_mxn}_{i,t}$$

$$F_{s,t} = \sum_{i \in s, \text{type}=\text{fixed}} \text{total_mxn}_{i,t}$$

$$R_{s,t} = \sum_{i \in s, \text{type}=\text{income}} \text{total_mxn}_{i,t}$$

Total costs are then the sum of the cost types:

$$C_{s,t} = I_{s,t} + V_{s,t} + F_{s,t}$$

And the net balance is defined as income minus costs:

$$NB_{s,t} = R_{s,t} - C_{s,t}$$

5.2 Financing modes

`Agent_Caf` supports a financing mode. Users can select the mode using the scenario: `financing_mode`.

- `implicit_balance`: a running balance is financed at interest rate i ; interest is charged on the outstanding balance each year.
- `transition_loan`: an explicit loan is issued at year 0, equal to the transition costs occurring before the farmer receives income from selling his crop (earliest year 3). The loan is repaid as equal principal installments over a time horizon that the user can choose.
- `none`: no financing costs are applied.

5.2.1 Implicit balance financing

Let B_t be the outstanding balance at the start of year t and i the annual interest rate. Interest is charged on the balance; surplus net cashflow repays the balance; deficits increase the balance.

$$\text{Interest}_t = i \times B_t$$

$$B_t^* = B_t + \text{Interest}_t$$

$$B_{t+1} = \begin{cases} B_t^* - \min(B_t^*, \text{NB}_t), & \text{NB}_t \geq 0 \\ B_t^* + (-\text{NB}_t), & \text{NB}_t < 0 \end{cases}$$

5.2.2 Transition loan financing

In transition_loan mode, the loan principal P is the sum of total costs over a user-selected set of basis years (default 0–2). Equal principal repayments are made over H years (horizon years) starting at year t_3 .

$$P = \sum_{t \in B} C_t$$

$$\text{PrincipalPay} = \frac{P}{H}$$

$$\text{Interest}_t = i \times \text{Balance}_t$$

$$\text{DebtService}_t = \text{Interest}_t + \text{PrincipalPay}_t$$

5.3 Total cashflow

System-level results (café, optional MILPA, Apiculture, cash-crops) are aggregated into a total model of cashflow by year. Optional 'extra income' (currently carbon revenue) is added after financing logic so that net cashflow is consistent with the chosen financing mode. Total income then becomes the sum of incomes by system plus the income from selling carbon credits:

$$R_t = \sum_s R_{s,t} + R_t^{\text{carbon}}$$

Similarly, total costs are the costs occurring for each system plus financing costs and the principal repayment:

$$C_t = \sum_s C_{s,t} + \text{FinancingCost}_t + \text{PrincipalRepay}_t$$

This leads to a total net cashflow:

$$CF_t = R_t - C_t$$

6. Financial indicators

6.1 Net Present Value (NPV)

We use a standard net present value calculation as a metric to represent the current worth of all future cash flows for the farmer. Net Present Value (NPV) converts a time series of net cashflows into a single present-value metric. It discounts future cashflows at a discount rate r , reflecting time preference and opportunity cost of capital. A positive NPV indicates that the investment is expected to generate value above the discount rate, supporting comparisons between alternative management options or financing arrangements.

$$NPV(r) = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

6.2 Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is used here to calculate the annual rate of growth of the farmers investment. The IRR can be expressed as the discount rate, r^* , that sets NPV to zero:

$$0 = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+r^*)^t}$$

7. Greenhouse gas emissions module

Agent_Caf computes annual GHG emissions from fertilizer applications – which are specified in type of fertilizer (organic, synthetic) and quantity in the parameter sheet. Emissions are calculated for several emission sources, converted to kg CO₂e/ha using stoichiometric conversion factors and Global Warming Potentials.

7.1 Direct emissions from synthetic fertilizer (N₂O)

Direct N₂O emissions from synthetic fertilizer application are calculated using the following formula:

$$E_t^{\text{direct}} = Q_t \times 0.001 \times N_{\text{app}} \times (1 - v) \times EF_{N_2O_N} \times CF_{N_2O_N} \times GWP_{N_2O}$$

Where:

- Q_t is fertilizer quantity (as defined in the parameter sheet) for year t .
- N_{app} is nitrogen application rate parameter.
- v is volatilization coefficient.
- EF_{N2O_N} is the emission factor for N2O-N.
- CF_{N2O_N} converts N2O-N to N2O (molecular weight conversion).
- GWP_{N2O} is the global warming potential of N₂O (kg CO₂e per kg N₂O).
- 0.001 converts from g to kg or aligns units as used in the project parameterization.

7.2 Indirect emissions from synthetic fertilizer (deposition and leaching)

Indirect emissions combine volatilized nitrogen deposition and leached nitrogen are calculated in the following manner:

$$E_t^{\text{indirect}} = (Q_t N_{app} v EF_{\text{depo}} + Q_t N_{app} f_{\text{leach}} EF_{\text{leach}}) \times (CF_{N2O_N} \times GWP_{N2O}) \times 0.001$$

7.3 Harvest residues and residue burning

The tool can include additional emission sources parameterized in the emission_parameter sheet, including emissions from harvest residues and crop residue burning. These equations use product-specific residue ratios, biomass fractions, oxidation fractions, and conversion factors to express CH₄, CO, N₂O, and NO_x emissions in CO₂e. Fertilization from manure is currently not yet included.

8. Biomass and carbon accounting module

Agent_Caf has two methods to account the carbon and CO₂ absorption from shade trees and coffee. *Method 1* reflects the allometric biomass equations used in the original excel model by Simonit et al. (2020). *Method 2* is based on findings in the literature for estimating aboveground biomass in tropical trees (Chave et al., 2014) and also Café Arabica plants (Negash et al., 2013). The authors also include methods to estimate belowground carbon absorption by shade trees and coffee based on root-to-shoot ratios developed by Kuyah et al (2012). Both methods can be selected in the model as scenario choices (carbon_absorption_method: "alt_chave_negash").

8.1 Tree density and growth trajectories

For both methods, tree density (plants/ha) is derived from econ_long for the coffee system (product = woody_species, input = plant). Biomass trajectories are read from biomass_parameter for a selected tree species (currently cedar in v1.0). In other words, CO₂ absorption currently only occurs from the cedar trees planted for the primary purpose of shade provision in the coffee agroforestry system. It does not include the potential absorption of trees from the existing forest that the coffee plants have been integrated into.

8.2 Allometric biomass equation and conversion to CO₂

Method 1 (Simonit et al. 2020):

For each year t, biomass per individual is computed from diameter (DBH) using an allometric equation:

$$B_t^{\text{ind}} = \exp(4.9375 + 1.0583 \ln(\text{DBH}_t^2)) \times \frac{1.14}{10^6}$$

Total aboveground biomass per hectare is then:

$$B_t^{\text{tot}} = B_t^{\text{ind}} \times D_t$$

Where D is the diameter of the tree.

Carbon stock and CO₂ equivalent are:

$$C_t = 0.47 \times B_t^{\text{tot}}$$

$$\text{CO}_{2t} = 3.67 \times C_t$$

These variables are multiplied by the vegetation planting density of trees to obtain carbon and CO₂ absorption per hectare.

Method 2 (Chave et al., 2014 and Negash et al., 2013):

Above-ground biomass (AGB) for shade trees is calculated as follows:

$$AGB_{st} = 0.0673 \times (p * DBH * H)^{0.976}$$

Where p is the wood-specific gravity density (0.48 g/cm³ for Cedar), and H is the height of the tree in each year.

Above-ground biomass for coffee plants (café arabica) is calculated as:

$$AGB_{cp} = 0.147 \times (d)^2$$

Where d is the tree diameter at different growth stages (3cm year 1-3, 5cm year 5 and 8cm at tree maturity).

Belowground biomass is based on root-to-shoot ratio of 1:5 for trees, resulting in BGB of 20% of the aboveground tree biomass:

$$BGB_{st} = ABG_{st} \times 0.20$$

Belowground biomass for coffee is based on the root-to-shoot ratio developed by Kuyah et al (2012):

$$BGB_{cp} = ABG_{cp} \times 0.28$$

We multiply the sum of aboveground and belowground biomass for trees and cafe by plantation density for trees and café and then multiply by carbon and CO2 conversion factors (0.49 and 3.76) to obtain the carbon stock and CO2 absorption per hectare.

8.3 Carbon revenue from incremental sequestration

This is an optional scenario. If enabled (scenario\$include_carbon_revenue = TRUE) and a positive carbon price is provided, the model computes annual carbon revenue from incremental CO₂ sequestration. Users can specify a carbon price (ton/ha) which is currently set to reflect the global CO₂ price (150MXN/ tCO₂):

$$\Delta CO2_t = \max(CO2_t - CO2_{t-1}, 0)$$

$$R_t^{\text{carbon}} = p_{CO2} \times \Delta CO2_t$$

8.4 Carbon balance

Carbon balance combines emissions (converted to tCO₂e/ha) and absorption (tCO₂/ha). In v1.0 the sign convention follows the implemented code in which absorption is added to (negative) emissions subtotals, producing a combined carbon_balance time series. Direct and indirect emissions are converted from kg to tons for the balance:

$$E_t^{\text{tot}} = \frac{E_t^{\text{dir}} + E_t^{\text{ind}}}{1000}$$

The total carbon balance is then the sum of total emissions (negative) and total CO₂ absorption from trees:

$$CB_t = E_t^{\text{tot}} + \Delta CO2_t$$

9. Results:

We provide here some primary results of specified scenario outputs to demonstrate the possibilities with the first version of the tool.

9.1 Replicating results from the original farm model: Model_Cafe_Arabica

First, we run Agent_CAF in `saberes_scenario` type = full and set `financing_mode` = none. This choice runs the finance and carbon balance calculations with input directly from the parameter sheet, without added scenario alterations, under optimum yield and should therefore replicate the results from the Oaxaca project. Table 2 lists a comparison of financial indicators at a discount rate of 4%, no CO₂ price and a time horizon of 20 years:

Table 2. Comparison of financial indicators Agent_Caf vs. original calculations:

Finance indicator	Agent_Caf	Original Model	Unit
updated_investment_cost	248.264,00	248.264,00	MXN/ha
transition_cost	263.910,52	221.835	MXN/ha
initial_financing_cost	0		MXN/ha
updated_total_cost	1.458.881,00	1.458.881,00	MXN/ha
rate_of_return	42,2	42,2	%
rate_of_return_project	42,2		%
current_net_value	1.738.151,00	1.738.151,00	MXN/ha
updated_total_benefits	3.197.032,00	3.197.032,00	MXN/ha

Here we can confirm that Agent_Caf does economic and financial calculations in consistency with the original model. The difference in transition cost is due to a slightly adjusted “logic” applied in Agent_Caf: the transition costs are calculated as the sum of all costs occurring during year 0 – 2, in the original Model_Cafe_Arabica the transition costs are limited to those costs occurring in year 0 only.

Figure 1: Cash-flow of the farm using all income sources (Farm replica)

Figure 2: Carbon Balance (Farm replica)

The carbon balance in Agent_Caf does NOT replicate the carbon balance in the Model_Cafe_Arabica. The reason is the following: We assume in Agent_Caf that the initial tree density of Cedar is the planting density of woody species (Cedar) = 30 and that no harvest occurs. In the carbon balance of Model_Cafe_Arabica the tree density is set to capture the density of Café_Arabica (3500) and then subtracts from this in year 1 the harvest quantity of tertiary stubbles (260). As a result the total carbon absorption of trees is much lower in Agent_Caf for the farm. However, to capture all CO2 absorption by trees we would want to include absorption rates from Café Arabica plants as well as cash crops (Banana, Cacao).

9.2: Module exploration: loan repayment, carbon revenues under moderate-low yields

If we switch system setting to “café_only” and turn on manually inclusion of MILPA, apiculture and cash-crops we would also be able to replicate above results. Here we run Agent_Caf with the inclusion of a transition_loan (repaid in 15 equal year installments at 3% interest rate). The loan is set to be equal to the transition costs. We also assume a scenario where yields for coffee drop to low-moderate, starting at year 6 to 18 (where it remains at 2.0 t/ha), due to adverse weather conditions (or to test the model in conditions where coffee production is slightly less favorable). The discount rate is set to 4%, as before. We immediately see the impact resulting in lower income, assuming the same sales price for coffee cherries as in the previous scenario. Important financial indicators show a lower return on investment (IRR drops to 38.5%) and current net value is about 17% lower:

Figure 3: Full farm model with moderate-low yield for coffee (2 ton/ha):

Table 3: finance indicators full farm model with moderate-low yields

Finance indicator	value	unit
updated_investment_cost	248.263,58	MXN/ha
transition_cost	263.910,52	MXN/ha
initial_financing_cost	0	MXN/ha
updated_total_cost	1.436.361,49	MXN/ha
rate_of_return	NA	%
rate_of_return_project	38,5	%
current_net_value	1.443.952,81	MXN/ha
updated_total_benefits	3.108.529,18	MXN/ha

9.3 Cafe Arabica production only under decreasing yield levels

Here we adjust the settings in Agent_Caf to system: “café_only” and turn off all additional income sources, but keep the loan repayment scheme scenario switched on. Hence, the only income source to the farmer is sales of coffee cherries at a fixed price (50 MXN/kg) given the annual quantity influenced by the yield scenarios. We provide results here for all yield scenarios (optimum, moderate, moderate_low, low) (*note: currently a minor bug sets yields higher in year 4 for moderate_low and low!*). While we see that farmers still operate under a positive net cashflow under three of the four yield scenarios, the relative magnitude of the loan repayment as an additional cost is clearly visible. In a hypothetical scenario where yields are set to the lowest boundary, farmers would technically operate under a negative cashflow, and most likely go bankrupt:

Table 4: Financial indicators under decreasing yields for café Arabica production

Financial indicator	optimum yield	moderate	moderat_low	low	unit
IRR	27,22	15,79	9,06	NA	%
NPV	571937,99	247173,20	-234641,21	294101,45	MXN/ha
updated_total_benefits	1539184,09	1214419,30	943781,97	673144,65	MXN/ha

Figure 4: Coffee- agroforestry system with no additional income at optimum coffee yield

Figure 5: Coffee- agroforestry system with no additional income at moderate coffee yield

Figure 6: Coffee- agroforestry system with no additional income at moderate-low coffee yield

Figure 7: Coffee- agroforestry system with no additional income at low coffee yield

10. Limitations and planned extensions

Agent_Caf in version 1.0 is limited by reading in technical parameters describing farm management across production cycles, costs and incomes from the Oaxaca Café Arabica model. It therefore requires significant modification and extension to be able to work as a model that allows application to different sites of coffee production in Mexico and beyond. This important generalization step would require a parameterization of cost factors to resemble input costs at different locations. CIMMYT data and work in a related project, BIOFincas can be a helpful starting point. Alongside updating cost of production, prices also need to be adjusted to specific locations. Here, statistical data at municipality level from SIAP can help. Eventually, it is foreseen that actual site-specific data can be used (farmer survey within SAbERES) to update the parameter sheet.

Summary of improvements:

- Yield reductions currently affect coffee income only. Yield-dependent harvest costs can be added later by applying the same multipliers to selected cost rows or other ideas that need to be implemented.
- Price adjustments to reflect local and regional prices for coffee using SIAP.
- Parameterization of costs (labour, fertilizer and other variable costs) to reflect regional changes in input costs. This can be done using CIMMYT economic account data.
- Biomass/absorption is currently demonstrated for one species (cedar). Extending to multiple species requires adding growth trajectories and selecting species in scenarios.
- Fully review the carbon balance model by experts or look to link finance/economic calculations to an existing carbon balance model for agroforestry
- Include scenarios for various tree density within agroforestry systems
- The emissions module is parameter-sheet driven; results depend on the quality and unit consistency of emission_parameter inputs. It also needs a review if these calculations are consistent and right. We need to add harvest residues and emissions from manure to be included!
- Future versions aim to add additional EbA systems (e.g., milpa with agroforestry, silvopasture etc)

11. References

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